

Review of Hokusai's *Abbreviated Drawing Manual* (*Manual de dibujo abreviado*) by Sans Soleil Ediciones

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BOOK DETAILS

- **ORIGINAL TITLE:** 略画早指南 —*Ryakuga Hayaoshie*—
- **EDITION TITLE (SPANISH):** *Manual de dibujo abreviado*
- **TITLE FOR ENGLISH READERS:** *Abbreviated Drawing Manual*
- **AUTHOR:** Katsushika Hokusai —1760–1849—. Edited by Vicente David Almazán Tomás —1971—
- **TRANSLATION (SPANISH):** Vicente David Almazán Tomás. Text proofreading by Isabel Mellén
- **GENRE:** Essay
- **PUBLISHER:** Sans Soleil Ediciones
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- **PAGES:** 112

Cover of *Abbreviated Drawing Manual*, by Sans Soleil Ediciones

Abbreviated Drawing Manual: The Value of Hokusai's Work

The Spanish publisher —based in Vitoria-Gasteiz— released in 2018 the Spanish edition of this book, part of the Wunderkammer collection —from German, “cabinet of wonders”—, dedicated both to visual works and silent novels, as well as to the work of printmakers and illustrators.

The volume under review is one of the manuals by the widely known Katsushika Hokusai —1760–1849—, and the most recent publication by the publisher focused on this artist, after Sans Soleil had previously published other works related to him, such as *One Hundred Views of Mount Fuji* (2016), reviewed by our colleague Sergio Paterna.

Today, Hokusai is recognized not only as a highly respected professional but also as a master of drawing, painting, and printmaking, whose unique approach to decomposing reality into geometric forms —sometimes unconventional— has influenced the training of countless artists both in Japan and the West.

His work is praised in design and fine arts schools by faculty members as an excellent example to teach students about simplification and deconstruction of forms in drawing, and as a framework applicable to other artistic practices, among many other virtues.

Most of Hokusai's works gained fame outside Japan posthumously, due to the tremendous popularity Japan achieved in the West after opening its borders to trade following the Tokugawa era. His work is associated with genres such as ukiyo-e and other works meant for mass reproduction, eagerly consumed by Japanese from different social classes, such as the chōnin —comparable to the Western lower and middle classes, like merchants.

In the West, artists like Toulouse-Lautrec and Van Gogh collected Hokusai's works and were influenced by them. However, as David Almazán emphasises in this book, it is important to understand that, although Hokusai is now respected and treated like other international artists, his life did not follow the same path as that of contemporaries elsewhere. While he experienced success during his lifetime, he was a restless individual who preferred not to settle in a single type of work or social position, and he primarily interacted with lower and middle social classes.

This Spanish edition of the manual includes material by Professor David Almazán, who provides an in-depth explanation of these aspects and contextualizes the images that appear throughout the pages —which we invite readers to explore in this review.

Abbreviated Drawing Manual: A Small but Great Collection of Hokusai's Works

Prolific as ever, Hokusai presents in this small but significant volume a collection of images on various topics. While the book offers a sufficient amount of his work, it is not an exhaustive volume; rather, it is a modest yet carefully curated collection chosen by Hokusai himself.

The illustrations respect Hokusai's original intentions —including their seemingly random order— and the selection was not decided by the publisher. Fortunately, quality outweighs quantity in this manual, although major finished works such as *The Great Wave off Kanagawa* (神奈川沖浪裏 —*Kanagawa oki nami ura*—) are not included. The illustrations are simpler, focusing on drawing and monochrome printmaking rather than finished paintings, colour prints, or full compositions.

As a propedeutic and methodological tool for understanding drawing, similar to Hokusai’s later works such as his *Hokusai Manga* collection (published from 1814 over 15 volumes), *Ryakuga Hayaoshie* —originally published in 1812— already demonstrates his approach to teaching future artists and promoting his work.

The manual focuses on creating illustrations from simple geometric shapes that evolve in complexity to produce the final work, covering themes such as animals, plants, Japanese cultural characters, and elements of folklore and traditional festivals —as well as some motifs from Chinese culture, with which Hokusai was also familiar.

This book is of interest not only to drawing enthusiasts and visual artists but also to those knowledgeable in Japanese culture. It serves as a teaching aid and as a foundation for illustrators and manga specialists, given that Hokusai’s work remains a cornerstone of Japanese comic art as we know it today.

The original 1812 edition was born from Hokusai’s desire to disseminate his art during his travels across Japan, marking his first major success and establishing him as a celebrated figure nationwide. Printed in black and white to reduce costs, this edition respects the visual clarity of Hokusai’s geometric forms, emphasizing the strength and importance of line and contour throughout the manual.

A Balanced Edition

Method for drawing an oni, Method for drawing a Hyotokko, and Method for drawing an okame. These works can be found both in the endpapers of the manual and within the collection of illustrations inside.

Graphic design was executed by Mikel Escalera and layout by Sandra Rodríguez García. Their work complements Hokusai’s art, producing a volume whose presentation, layout, and internal structuring demonstrate full respect for the original artist. The cover itself reflects the interior’s visual motifs, with several of Hokusai’s black-and-white works incorporated, seamlessly integrating the artist’s name and the publisher into the design.

Upon opening the book, we first encounter several examples of geometric deconstruction on the endpapers —works such as a *Method for drawing an oni* appear here, and we will see them again in full glory within the manual— which once again hint at what awaits us throughout the rest of the volume.

The type of paper chosen is matte, intended to avoid distracting the reader with unnecessary glare, and it enhances the powerful blacks of Hokusai’s lines, as the paper is not pure white but has a slightly off-white, bone-coloured tone. All of this reinforces the

book’s nature as a drawing manual. The touch of colour comes from the magenta book band, with large white letters bearing the subtitle “Learn to Draw with Hokusai,” and the publisher’s name on the back, all set against waves drawn by the Japanese master.

Placing the introduction at the very beginning of the volume and making readers wait before enjoying more of the artist's images is a clear demonstration of the book's didactic intent. An expert in Hokusai's work could skip the introduction —though this is not recommended— to go straight to his works. However, someone who is simply a fan or new to the Japanese engraver's work, or even Japanese art in general, will first benefit from the wealth of details compiled by Professor David Almazán Tomás and included in the book for the delight and enrichment of readers.

Throughout the various illustrations, we see plants, flowers, animals —such as the lions that open Hokusai's collection—, characters like priests, peasants, men and women in typical period attire, and objects such as Daruma dolls, sometimes depicted humorously to amuse and surprise the viewer. Alongside each final version of a subject, we can observe its decomposition into simpler geometric shapes, like circles, and the supporting lines used in the final composition. All image sets are framed within black rectangles, reminiscent of the panels we now see in contemporary manga.

On several occasions, Hokusai chooses to use geometric shapes to contain the depicted element rather than to construct it, as seen in the illustration titled *Method for Drawing a Puppy with a Compass*. In many other examples, he employs compositions and combinations far more complex than the final illustration, revealing that the finished work is actually the result of significant simplification by the master.

It is also common for Hokusai to include examples in the manual of geometric shapes that, at first glance, might not be the choice of any ordinary artist when simplifying a character or element. Yet, as seen in the accompanying images, these choices make sense when observing how they function in the final illustration —for instance, plate 24, *Method for Drawing Roosters Using Squares*, shown below these lines.

In this image, *Method for Drawing a Hare Crossing the Waves* and *Method for Drawing Roosters Using Squares*

Different “games” that the artist uses to present a drawing as a curiosity can be seen in illustrations such as *Method for Composing Small Birds from the Shape of an Egg* or *The Butterfly’s Dance*, and sometimes, even when there is a final illustration showing a character, the abstraction remains predominant, and the character continues to be almost hidden beneath the geometric forms, as happens in works contained in the book, such as *Method for Representing a River Fisherman*.

After completing the collection of illustrations, Almazán incorporates a series of comments about them, specifying certain aspects of the works, such as why Hokusai arranged them in a seemingly random order—as the professor explains. As Almazán notes, Hokusai rarely gave instructions or showed the complete process of the illustration, perhaps assuming that the reader of his manual already possessed certain drawing skills, thus emphasizing the visual power of the illustrations themselves.

Almazán’s contribution enhances the work as a whole

One of the aspects to highlight and appreciate in this Spanish edition of the *Abbreviated Drawing Manual* is the remarkable work of Dr. Vicente David Almazán Tomás, professor of Japanese art in the Department of Art History at the University of Zaragoza. His doctoral thesis, published in 2000 and titled *Japan and Japonism in Spanish Illustrated Magazines (1870–1935)—Japón y el japonismo en las revistas ilustradas españolas (1870–1935)*—, already demonstrates his deep understanding of Japanese culture.

Throughout his commentary and the book’s introduction, Almazán provides a brief overview of Hokusai’s life and work, while also discussing the Japanese society in which the artist lived, and the contemporary relevance of his oeuvre, which remains widely exhibited today, as Almazán notes. Hokusai was a man of his time, as the professor emphasizes, dedicating himself to producing prints and engravings on a variety of subjects, including historical and mythological Japanese figures, actors and actresses, and notable locations in Japan.

Almazán also details the original Japanese edition of this book published during Hokusai’s lifetime, presenting the information clearly and concisely, accessible even to readers without specialized knowledge or high academic training. The author includes numerous Japanese terms that do not have direct translations—terms he explains carefully—and incorporates various notes to help readers understand concepts from Japanese culture and Hokusai’s art in particular.

This is followed by a list of the figures found in the manual, and then the real magic begins as readers are fully immersed in Hokusai’s illustrations. Despite all of the notes and explanations provided by the professor, we recommend this book primarily to readers with some prior knowledge of Japan, so they are not constantly seeking external information while reading. Those versed in Japanese culture will enjoy it much more, although it remains suitable for nearly any type of reader.

After completing the manual’s illustration collection, David Almazán proceeds to explain each figure in the section *Comments on the Figures*, offering insights valuable both for connoisseurs of Japanese culture and Hokusai’s work, as well as for novices.

He explains how the artist created the illustrations, what appears in them, and why he represented each subject in the way he did, shedding light on various elements of Japanese tradition. For example, he discusses the significance of certain flowers, such as the lily, the cultural importance of animals like the crane or octopus —the latter also in Japanese cuisine—, the origin of the lions depicted in the manual, and objects such as Daruma dolls. He also explains how certain images or stylistic choices by Hokusai influenced later trends —including caricature, stylization, manga drawing, and contemporary kawaii aesthetics.

Additionally, Almazán translates the notes that Hokusai himself included in his illustrations, in which the artist offered guidance or explained aspects of the process for creating each drawing. This proves extremely enriching, as it allows readers to gain a much deeper understanding of each illustration, whether they are enthusiasts or new to Japanese culture.

Method for drawing lions using circles and Method for composing small birds from the shape of an egg

Average rating: 86/100

- **Literary quality:** 90/100
- **Narrative flow:** 85/100
- **Edition:** 90/100
- **Reader accessibility:** 95/100
- **Overall relevance:** 70/100

Abbreviated Drawing Manual

Undoubtedly, a must-have book for enthusiasts of Katsushika Hokusai's work, and highly useful as supplementary material for teaching drawing. It is also quite recommended for readers unfamiliar with Japanese culture or the artist's oeuvre.

An impeccably edited work, in such a way, that we can only express our deepest respect for the efforts of Dr. David Almazán and the rest of the team for their dedication and enthusiasm for Hokusai's work. While it cannot be considered the artist's definitive work, it is a significant addition for any enthusiast or collector of books and compendiums on traditional Japanese art.

Sources

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